

A taster of in situ spatial transcriptomics experimental analysis

Workshop

25 Feb 2026

Single cell Spatial

The technologies are maturing
=> **real experimental design**

Spatial flavours

spot-based spatial omics

Visium, Visuim HD, Stereo-seq

Whole transcriptome (seq or probe)

“Binned” pools of cells

Image-based spatial omics

Xenium, CosMx, MERFISH

RNA probes: 100 – 6000 – (to 20000?)

Protein: 10s-100s

Cells segmented – single cell and subcellular resolution

What is this workshop?

A taster of in situ spatial transcriptomics experimental analysis

We will start with a pre-processed dataset and try out some tests across experimental conditions

- Tour of common options for spatial analyses
- Visualisations

Aimed at newcomers to spatial analyses.

QCIF

Australian
BioCommons

THE UNIVERSITY OF
SYDNEY

Workshop Logistics

2 hour workshop

- All work will be on the provided VMs
- A preprocessed dataset is on the VMs
 - NB: The VMs are small – The long running steps have been preprepared.
- We will work through a number of Rmarkdown files together

Trainers

- Sarah Williams (QCIF)
- Frederick Jaya (Sydney Informatics Hub, USYD)
- James Sinclair (Griffith University)

What we will cover

What we will cover

What we won't cover

- Loading raw data
- Image analysis methods:
Segmentation, image registration,
e.t.c
- Pre-processing: QC, filtering and
building a UMAP
- Cell type annotation
- Other omic data: – just
RNA – no p

A previous

Preprocessing

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Workshop:

Spatial Sampler

More resources for comparative tests

- Worked example/how-tos
- Code snippets
- Seurat and SFE based examples
- <https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/index.html>

Spatial Sampler

Single cell resolution spatial technologies like CosMx, Xenium, vizgen and STOmics have moved past the technology demo stages, and are now being applied to real world biological research problems. Many [excellent resources](#) cover the preprocessing spatial data from these platforms, and many more package vignettes cover specific tools.

Spatial sampler is instead a collection of How-Tos framed around testing specific biological questions – i.e. comparative tests between experimental conditions.

Each HowTo includes:

- A **worked example** using a real dataset, which explains why each step is necessary
- What **input data** is needed
- What the **output** looks like
- A **code snippet** that can be copy-pasted

Explore these HowTos with the searchable table below.

	Description	Technology	Toolkit

But some preprocessing resources...

A curated list of introductory resources	https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/g_tutorials.html
Preprocessing using Seurat (workshop)	https://swbioinf.github.io/intro-spatial-transcriptomics-workshop/index.html
Preprocessing using Bioconductor (vignette)	https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/d_cosmxIBD_sfe.html
Example of cell type assignment using Bioconductor (vignette)	https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/e_celltypeannotation_sfe.html
Spatial sampler - Examples of hypothesis tests	https://swbioinf.github.io/spatialsnippets/index.html

The workshop data

The Study: IBD Colon

Garrido-Trigo et al (2023) : *Macrophage and neutrophil heterogeneity at single-cell spatial resolution in human inflammatory bowel disease*

Paper:
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-023-40156-6>

Data:
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE234713>

Code:
https://github.com/ibd-bcn/ibd-bcn_single_cell

nature communications

Article

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-40156-6>

Macrophage and neutrophil heterogeneity at single-cell spatial resolution in human inflammatory bowel disease

Received: 5 January 2023

Accepted: 14 July 2023

Published online: 26 July 2023

Check for updates

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Experimental Design

- 9 Samples: 3x Crohn's Disease, 3x Ulcerative Colitis, 3x Healthy Controls
- One sample per slide
- CosMx 1k gene panel

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Workshop

CD_a

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

CD_b

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

CD_c

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

HC_a

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

HC_b

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

HC_c

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

UC_a

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

UC_b

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

UC_c

epi
myeloids
plasmas
stroma
tcells

Thank you!

Bioinformatics

- Genomics/Transcriptomics
- Single-cell/Spatial Omics
- Metagenomics
- Multi-omics integration

Data & Software

- Data Architecture and Design
- Data Analytics
- Software Development
- Sensitive Data Management

Applied AI & Quantum

- AI/Quantum for Bioinformatics
- AI for Health
- Quantum Optimisation Complex Systems
- Federated Machine Learning

Statistics

- RCT's and Observational Studies
- Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis
- Predictive Modelling and Machine Learning
- Factor Analysis

Qualitative Research

- Qualitative Research Consultancy & Partnerships
- Technical upskilling for researchers

Skills & Training

- Training in Programming, statistics, machine learning, data management, and bioinformatics
- Communities of Practice
- Internship Programs

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